

SEADOTS

Social-Ecological Ocean Management Applications using Digital Ocean Twins

Empowering Sustainable Ocean Governance Through Digital Innovation

Decision support tools
for marine
spatial planning

Aligning with
the EU Green Deal
and UN Ocean
Decade goals

Social-Ecological Ocean Management Applications using Digital Ocean Twins integrates social-ecological data with advanced technologies to develop sustainable ocean management solutions.

9 partners
from 8 countries
Focus regions

Norwegian North Sea

Swedish Baltic Sea

German North Sea

Get involved

Visit our website or follow us on social media to stay updated on SEADOTS' progress.

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